

A General Model for Creation (and Miscreation)

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Abstract

In this paper we first excerpt some metaphysical passages from the work known as *A Course in Miracles* (ACIM), and use them to construct a basic creation model for (what is presumably) the first-created world. Upon comparing this model with a previously-developed fundamental model for constructing the physical universe, we find that the first-created world and the physical universe are apparently just different instances of the same creation paradigm — an astonishing result, yet one that is favored by the principle of parsimony. We summarize these results in the form of a general model for creating worlds. Then, with the help of many additional ACIM passages, we go on to explore deeper metaphysical aspects of creation (and miscreation).

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1 Introduction

In two previous papers ([1], [2]), we developed a fundamental model, called “system P”, for constructing the physical universe.¹ Assuming the basic correctness of that model, the question naturally arises: Is it a *one-off* model that applies only to construction of the physical universe, or does it apply more generally? That is, if there are other created worlds in existence, do they follow this same model, or different models?

In this paper, we show that at least one other purported world seems to follow the system-P paradigm: the world that is described in the work known as *A Course in Miracles* (ACIM), which is presumably the *very-first* created world. Although ACIM deals mainly with *psychology*, it also contains a lot of (cryptic) *metaphysical* material, including about the process of creation itself. The purported source/author of ACIM is the historical Jesus.

We will gather some metaphysical excerpts from ACIM and use them to outline a construction model for the first-created world. Remarkably, we will find that this first-created

¹Note that the present paper is quite self-contained, so it can be read *before* [1] and [2].

world, and the physical universe (as constructed via system P), appear to be just different instances of the *same* creation model — indicating that we have possibly uncovered a truly general and unified model for creation. We will then go on to explore deeper metaphysical aspects of both the first-created world and the physical universe, including their ontological relation to each other.

Before proceeding with the main development, it will be useful to summarize some basic metaphysical principles from the system-P paper. In addition, a brief history of ACIM will also be helpful.

2 Metaphysical preliminaries

An important concept in the system-P model, which will also be important for the metaphysics in the present paper, is called **ontological priority**, defined as follows [3]:

“*A is ontologically prior to B*” means that *A* is (ontologically/existentially) *independent* of *B*, whereas *B* is (ontologically/existentially) *dependent* on *A*. (Alternatively, we may convey the same meaning by saying that “*B* is ontologically *subsequent* to *A*”.)

Unless otherwise indicated, the terms “prior” and “priority” in this paper will typically refer to relations of *ontological* priority (i.e., *not* temporal priority); and the terms “subsequent” or “subsequence” will refer to *ontological* subsequence.

Now suppose that the things of a given system are related by ontological priority and subsequence, and let *x* be a thing of that system. Wherever *x* is **in effect** or **operant** is called the **scope** of *x*. Wherever *x* is *not* operant is *outside* the scope of *x*.

By the definition of ontological priority above, things that are *subsequent* to *x* are (ontologically) *dependent* on *x*, and thus within the scope of *x*. Conversely, things that are *prior* to *x* are *independent* of *x*, and thus outside the scope of *x*. All of this is summarized in what will be called the **scope rule**, stated as follows:

A thing of the system is in effect/operant at (i.e. contains within its scope) those things that are *subsequent*, but is not in effect at (does not contain within its scope) those things that are *prior*.

The following corollary of the scope rule will be called the **nesting rule**:

A subsequent thing is ontologically **nested** (and thus embedded, contained, encapsulated, confined) *within* the scope of a prior thing; and, conversely, a prior thing contains, encapsulates and confines (within its scope) a subsequent thing.

Another corollary of the scope rule will be called the **inheritance rule**, as follows:

Suppose something called q is in effect/operant for the thing x , where q might be a set of one or more elements of the system, or an associated attribute, characteristic, property, or process. By the scope rule, q is also operant for things that are *subsequent* to x . Thus, except for their reduced scopes, we can say that those subsequent things *inherit* everything that is operant for x .

In summary, such scope, nesting, and inheritance properties are indicative of a system whose things/entities/components/processes are related by ontological priority and subsequence.

Finally, if a is prior to b , and b is prior to c , then we will say that their **order of priority** is: a , b , c .

3 A brief history of ACIM

One evening in October 1965, Dr. Helen Schucman, a psychologist at Columbia-Presbyterian Medical Center in New York City [4, pp.77-9], experienced what she described as an inner voice or “dictation”, which began by saying, “This is a course in miracles, please take notes.” [4, pp.179-82], [5, p.6] Somewhat distressed by this, she telephoned her Medical-Center colleague, Dr. William Thetford, also a psychologist (and Director of the Clinical Psychology Department) [6, p.331], [7]. He advised her to write down what the voice was saying and bring the notes to work the next day where they would both evaluate them [4, p.180],[6, p.80]. Astonished by the content of those first notes, the two of them began a long collaboration in which Schucman would write down the notes from the voice in shorthand, and at some later time read them off to Thetford, who would type them onto paper [6, p.80], [8, p.1], [5, pp.6-7]. It was apparent to Schucman (the “scribe”) that the inner voice was that of the historical Jesus [4, p.179], [5, p.6].

The result of this collaboration, after seven years, was what they called the “Urtext” of *A Course in Miracles*, consisting of three volumes: the *Text*, the *Workbook for Students*, and the *Manual for Teachers* [8, p.3]. This material was then edited by Schucman and Thetford to produce a manuscript, a copy of which (in 1972) was sent to Hugh Lynn Cayce (son of Edgar Cayce); as such, this version of ACIM was dubbed the “Hugh Lynn [Cayce] version”, commonly abbreviated as either HLV or HLC [4, p.114], [9]. In 1973, Dr. Kenneth Wapnick, another psychologist, came on the scene and, after reading the HLV manuscript, suggested that further editing was needed to prepare the work for actual publication [4, p.347], [6, p.102]. The result of this editing process was what became the First Edition of *A Course in Miracles*, published in 1976 [4, pp.355,487], [9]. Second and Third Editions were subsequently published in 1992 and 2007 [10].

In the year 2000, copies of the HLV and the *Text* volume of the Urtext (previously unavailable to the general public) were leaked onto the Internet [9].² By comparing these with

²As the result of a U.S. Federal Court Opinion in 2003, these early ACIM materials were deemed to have entered the public domain [5].

the published editions, it became apparent that much editing had been performed to prepare the official *Text* volume of ACIM; however, the *Workbook* and *Manual* volumes purportedly came through the editing process essentially intact [9]. I won't get into the discussion about which version of ACIM is "best"; I will simply say that the Urtext version of the *Text* volume is more suitable for our present purposes, which are mainly *metaphysical* (in contrast to the purpose of ACIM, which, as already alluded to, is mainly psychological).

In what follows, I will be quoting passages from, and using the pagination of, the following (freely downloadable) *Text* volume of the Urtext: [11]. I will also be quoting passages from the *Workbook for Students* and the *Manual for Teachers* that are found in the following (freely downloadable) version of ACIM: [12]. Passages from the *Text* will be cited as "Text" and page number; passages from the *Workbook for Students* will be cited as "W-" and section number; and passages from the *Manual for Teachers* will be cited as "M-" and section number.

Note also that, for passages excerpted from the *Text*, I am using *italics* — instead of the original capitalization — for emphasis. In addition, unless otherwise noted or evident from the particular context, the terms "you", "we", "I", "me", "my", etc., in ACIM passages refer *not* to the physical bodies that we are currently associated with, but to our souls and minds.

4 Aspects of the first-created system and world, and parallels with system/world P

Consider the following passages from ACIM:

1. Projection is a fundamental law ... which *always* operates. It is the law by which you ... were created. (Text, p. 174)
2. God created you as part of Him. (Text, p. 146)

These two passages indicate that the process of creation fundamentally involves "projection" of some kind; and, indeed, that God used such projection to create *us* (i.e. our souls). Likewise, in [2], the paradigm (called system P) for constructing the *physical universe* fundamentally involves "displacement" of a particular kind (i.e., displacement from a prior level). Since there is a sense of the term projection³ that has a similar connotation to the term displacement, then this is the first hint of a parallel between the construction process for the first-created world and the construction process for the physical universe.

Now consider the following additional passages from ACIM:

3. Projection...is a fundamental attribute of God, which he also gave to his Son. In the creation, God projected his creative ability out of Himself toward the souls which He created, ... (Text, p. 601)
4. God has but one Son... (Text, p. 209)

³I.e., "a thing or part that extends outward" [13] (and see Text, p. 600).

5. Christ is the Son of God, who lives in his Creator ... (Text, p. 230)
6. Every child of God [e.g. soul] is one in Christ, for his being is in Christ, as Christ's is in God. (Text, p. 250)
7. God...encompasses *all* Being... (Text, p. 120)

Passage 3 affirms the fundamental role of “projection” in creation; and indicates the creation/existence of a “Son” (singular) and “souls” (plural). Passage 4 affirms that this Son is a *single* entity, to which passage 5 attaches the name “Christ”. In addition, passage 5 indicates that this single entity — the one Son, or Christ — is nested/embedded *within* God. Passage 6 then reveals such nesting to be a basic relationship between the children of God (souls), the one Son (Christ), and the Creator (God): that is, the souls are (ontologically) nested/embedded *within* Christ, who is nested/embedded *within* God. Finally, passage 7 indicates that *all* of creation is nested within God. Passages 5, 6, and 7 are thus clear examples of *ontological nesting* in the first-created world.

The following ACIM passages (along with passage 3 above) abundantly reveal *inheritance* in this system/world:

Christ ... is the Self that God created as His only Son. (Text, p. 571)

...God shares His Self with Christ. (Text, p. 313)

the Self which is God's only Son, [was created in] the likeness of ... [God]. (W-322.1)

Christ ... is [God's] Son, and my true Self as well. (W-237.2.)

Christ is the Self the Sonship shares, as God shares His Self with Christ. (Text, p. 313)

I have no self except the Christ in me. ...who is Christ except [God's] Son as [God] created Him? ...what am I except the Christ in me? (W-354)

Christ ... [is] my Identity ... [and] my Self. (W-353.1)

The Son of God is my Identity. (W-252)

the Son of God ... Who is our own Identity. (W-269.2)

the Word, the Name which God has given you; the one Identity which all things share... (W-184.10)

The Name of God is my inheritance. (W-184)

I am in the likeness of my Creator. (W-84.2)

all [God's] attributes abide in me... (W-326)

God, who encompasses *all* Being, nevertheless created separate beings who have everything individually... (Text, p. 120)

In summary, these passages mean the following: Christ inherited his Identity/Self (e.g. nature, qualities, characteristics, attributes) from God; and, in turn, we (the many Sons, or souls) inherited the same from Christ. The result is that Christ is a being/entity in the likeness of God, and we are beings/entities in the likeness of Christ (and thus, also, in the likeness of God). Additionally, the passages indicate that we, the many souls, all *share* the *same* identity/self, which we inherited from Christ, who inherited it from God. Indeed:

your identity is shared... (Text, p. 205)

your identity ... is shared. (Text, p. 300)

we [are] One in shared Identity... (W-283.2)

Each of the next three passages reflects *both* nesting and inheritance in the first-created world:

God created you as part of *Him*. That is both *where* you are and *what* you are. ... everything was created *by* [God] and *in* [God]. (Text, p. 146)

God is everywhere, and His Son is *in* Him *with* everything. (Text, p. 283)

God is all in all ... (Text, p. 166)

As described in section 2, such nesting and inheritance will occur when the things of a system are related by ontological priority and subsequence. So a simple interpretation of the above ACIM passages is that God is (ontologically) prior to Christ, and Christ is prior to the souls. From the definition of ontological priority, we can also say that: God is (existentially) independent of Christ, who is independent of the souls; and, conversely, the souls are dependent on Christ, who is dependent on God. Moreover, we can take passage 6 to mean that the souls are nested within the *scope* of Christ, who in turn is nested within the scope of God. And we can take passage 7 as indicating that *all* of creation is nested within the scope of God.

We have so far identified three kinds of beings in the first-created system/world: God, the Creator; the one Son, or Christ; and a plurality of souls⁴. Moreover, since creation in this system clearly emanates *from* God, then God is an *uncreated* entity of that system⁵; whereas Christ and the souls are *created* entities. The order of priority is clearly: God, Christ, souls. Apparently then, God first creates Christ (via projection), and then creates the souls (via further projection).

Consider now the passage:

⁴Given that there are around 7 billion people here on earth, each of whom presumably has one soul, then we can safely estimate the number of souls to be at least in the many billions. Thus there is a single God and a single Christ, but *many* souls.

⁵And since it is the *very-first* created system, then God is simply *uncreated*.

You were created above the angels... (Text, p. 24)

This passage indicates the existence of a *fourth* kind of being in the first-created system, which we (the souls) were created “above”. In the context of our previous findings, we will take the term “above” in this passage to mean “ontologically prior to”. Thus, in this sense, God is above Christ, and Christ is above our souls. So, for the passage to say that we “were created above the angels” means that we (the many souls) were created *prior to* the angels; or equivalently, the angels were created subsequent to us. Hence, the order of priority is: God, Christ, souls, angels.

Let us denote an entity’s *place* in this ordering scheme as a *level* of the system, labeled 0, 1, 2, and 3. Thus, God is the single entity/being at level 0 of the system; Christ is the single being at level 1; the souls are beings at level 2; and the angels are beings at level 3. Since projection is the fundamental means of creation, then (as already alluded to above) this sequence of beings is presumably created by a sequence of projections. Let us label the projections in this sequence as \mathbf{d}_{0c} , \mathbf{d}_{1c} , and \mathbf{d}_{2c} ; where the letter c in the subscripts indicate that these are projections for constructing the first-*C*reated world — which may therefore also be called “world C”, and the system that constructs it may be called “system C”.

Thus, \mathbf{d}_{0c} is a projection from level 0 (God), which yields level 1 and its single entity, Christ; \mathbf{d}_{1c} is a projection from level 1, which yields level 2 and its entities, the souls; and \mathbf{d}_{2c} is a projection from level 2, which yields level 3 and its entities, the angels. As with the displacements in system P, since these projections have a kind of *direction* (i.e. they point from a prior level to a subsequent level), then we can take them as one-dimensional *vectors*. Fig. 1 illustrates the basic structure that is created by this scheme, where the projections are represented by vertical arrows from a prior level to a subsequent level, and the sequence of projections that is needed to create a given level is shown to the right of that level. Fig. 2 then shows the entities/beings that we have associated with each level.⁶

Fig. 1: Construction of levels 1 through 3 of the first-created system/world (i.e. system/world C), via the projection sequence $(\mathbf{d}_{0c}, \mathbf{d}_{1c}, \mathbf{d}_{2c})$. The projection sequence that is required to construct a given level is shown to the right of that level.

⁶To keep things simple going forward, for the first-created world we will typically focus on levels 0, 1, and 2, and their respective entities/beings — God, Christ, and souls.

Fig. 2: The entities/beings of the first-created system/world. God is the single (uncreated) being at level 0; Christ is the single being at level 1; the many souls are beings at level 2; and the many angels are beings at level 3.

In parallel with system P [2], the projection \mathbf{d}_{1c} will see the projection \mathbf{d}_{0c} as *three* dimensional, thereby yielding (at level 2 and above) an ordinary 3-dimensional space for the first-created world. Conversely, \mathbf{d}_{0c} will see \mathbf{d}_{1c} as *one* dimensional, yielding (at level 2 and above) the ordinary *time* dimension for this world. Thus, as with system P (and due to the scope rule), the ordinary space and time of the first-created world are operant at level 2 and above (i.e., they are *native* to level 2).

Since Christ is a *level-1* entity, but the ordinary space of the system is native to *level 2*, then Christ is prior to, and thus independent of, that space. And so, by reasoning that was developed in [1] and [2], we conclude that Christ must manifest ubiquitously, uniformly, and continuously throughout the ordinary space of the first-created world. Therefore, entities/beings at level 2 and above (i.e. souls and angels) will see Christ as a ubiquitous, uniform, and continuous entity in which (as affirmed by passage 6) they are nested/embedded.

Figures 1 and 2 here should be compared directly with Figures 1 and 2 in the system-P paper [2]. In particular, we found in that paper that dark energy is a *single* entity at level 1 which manifests ubiquitously, uniformly, and continuously throughout the ordinary space of the physical universe. Thus we have the astonishing result that dark energy in the physical world is the counterpart of Christ in the first-created world. Moreover, leptons (e.g. electrons) in the physical world are counterparts of souls in the first-created world; and baryons (e.g. protons and neutrons) in the physical world are counterparts of angels in the first-created world.

The production of a single entity at level 1, and a plurality of entities at each subsequent level therefore seems to be characteristic of a *general* (or generic) model for creation, of which the first-created world and the physical universe are particular instances. Given the parallels between these two worlds, then we may take the terms “displacement” and “projection” to be metaphysically equivalent and/or interchangeable, although we will typically use the former term in reference to the primitive constructive elements of the physical universe (system/world P).⁷ In any case, nothing less than astonishment is the proper reaction to such

⁷Note that, as already mentioned, ACIM is mainly about psychology; and the original interpreters/editors of ACIM (including Schucman and Wapnick) were all psychologists from the Freudian school. So naturally

parallels between the first-created world of Christ, souls, and angels (described in ACIM) and the physical world of dark energy and particles (described in [1] and [2]). On the other hand, despite our natural astonishment, the principle of parsimony *does* favor a *single* paradigm for creation, instead of many different paradigms; so we should not be *too* surprised by this result.

Finally, consider the following passage:

It should be noted that God *has* begotten only *one* Son. ...all of the souls that God created are His Sons... (Text, p. 65)

Although this passage might seem self-contradictory at first glance, our previous results allow the following consistent interpretation: The first projection (or, if you will, *generation*), \mathbf{d}_{0c} , creates a *single* entity (at level 1) — the so-called “*one* Son”, or Christ. The second projection/generation, \mathbf{d}_{1c} , then creates many “souls” (at level 2), who each inherit the *complete* nature/likeness/attributes of the “one Son” — and so, in this sense, can themselves be called “Sons” of God. In other words, we might say that Christ (at level 1) is the *prototype* Son, whose identity/self is inherited completely by each of the many souls (at level 2), thereby yielding *many* “Sons”.

4.1 A technical theology

As with displacements in system P, we can take the set of projections that construct (and are operant at) a given level to be the “genome” of an object/entity/being at that level. Thus we can take the set $\{ \}$ to be the genome for God at level 0; the set $\{ \mathbf{d}_{0c} \}$ to be the genome for Christ at level 1; the set $\{ \mathbf{d}_{0c}, \mathbf{d}_{1c} \}$ to be the genome for souls at level 2; and the set $\{ \mathbf{d}_{0c}, \mathbf{d}_{1c}, \mathbf{d}_{2c} \}$ to be the genome for angels at level 3.

Since the terms God, Christ, souls, and angels typically come with a lot of conditioned connotations and interpretations (i.e. “baggage”), then it is warranted to present alternative, technical terms for these entities/beings — so that (if desired) the present model can be discussed and evaluated on a purely metaphysical and technical basis.

Given that God is the “Entity at level 0 of system C”, then a technical term for God could be “El0sc”; which, if we substitute the letter ‘o’ in place of the number 0, may be written/pronounced as “Elosc”. Likewise, Christ is the “Entity at level 1 of system C”, or “El1sc”; which, if we substitute the letter ‘i’ in place of the number 1, may be written/pronounced as “Elisc”. The souls are “entities at level 2 of system C”, or “el2sc”; which, if we substitute the letter ‘u’ in place of the number 2 (since a 2 can be rotated to

they interpreted the term “projection” exclusively in the negative, Freudian, psychological sense (i.e., as an ego defense mechanism), and employed the term that way in the officially-published versions of ACIM. However, as exhibited in the above-quoted passages, the unedited (or, perhaps, *minimally* edited) *Text* volume of the Urtext [11] clearly uses the term projection in a more general, metaphysical sense — as an essential element in the creation process. A deeper understanding reveals that these two senses of the term — psychological and metaphysical — are actually *consistent*; i.e., projection as an ego defense mechanism is just a *miscreative* use of the (normally creative) projection process. More about miscreation in sections 8, 9, and 10.

look like a ‘u’), may be written/pronounced as “elusc”⁸. Finally, the angels are “entities at level 3 of system C”, or “el3sc”; which, if we substitute the letter ‘e’ in place of the number 3, may be written/pronounced as “elesc”.

Table 1 summarizes the above technical results for the entities/beings of the first-created system/world.

Level	Conventional name	Technical names	Genome
3	angel	el3sc / elesc	$\{\mathbf{d}_{0c}, \mathbf{d}_{1c}, \mathbf{d}_{2c}\}$
2	soul	el2sc / elusc	$\{\mathbf{d}_{0c}, \mathbf{d}_{1c}\}$
1	Christ	El1sc / Elisc	$\{\mathbf{d}_{0c}\}$
0	God	El0sc / Elosc	$\{\}$

Table 1: Technical aspects of the different entities/beings of the first-created world (i.e. world C).

4.2 A general model for creating worlds

Given the commonalities between systems C and P, we propose the following *general/generic* model for creating a world. We start by adapting the first four postulates of system P [2] for the general case:

1. The primitive element for creating a world is a type of *displacement* (or *projection*). Specifically: *displacement/projection from a prior level*.
2. The primitive structure is a *sequence* of such displacements/projections.
3. Each displacement/projection is a *one-dimensional vector*, constituting a *different*, but related, one-dimensional space. (The basic relations between these displacements/projections/vectors are stated in the next postulate.)
4. Prior things (e.g. displacements/projections, levels, and constructions from them) are *independent of* subsequent things; and, conversely, subsequent things are *dependent on* prior things. (The terms “prior” and “subsequent” denote here *ontological* relations, *not* temporal relations. See the definition of “ontological priority” in section 2; and also see [3] for a more detailed explication.)

This model constructs the system shown in Fig. 3, and yields a general/generic world — which may be called system/world G.

System/world C (i.e. the first-created world, as described in ACIM and above) is thus the first instance of this general model, for which $m = 3$; and system/world P (the physical universe, as described in [2]) is an instance of this general model for which $m = 3$ or 4.

⁸A helpful mnemonic is thus **elusc**; i.e., the beings at level 2 are the souls, and therefore **us**.

Fig. 3: Construction of levels 1 through m via the displacement/projection sequence $(\mathbf{d}_{0g}, \mathbf{d}_{1g}, \dots, \mathbf{d}_{(m-1)g})$, yielding the generic system/world G . The projection sequence that is required to construct a given level is shown to the right of that level.

In all such instances, the second displacement/projection (\mathbf{d}_{1g}) sees the first (\mathbf{d}_{0g}) as the 3-dimensional ordinary space of the system; and the first sees the second as the 1-dimensional ordinary time for the system/world.

Due to postulate 4, the scope, nesting, and inheritance rules apply for such a generic world, as we have found for the instances C and P.

5 Further aspects of creation

5.1 Mind as the creative agent

The following passages reveal that perhaps the best single concept for describing the nature of God, Christ, and ourselves (the many souls) is *mind* — which, as we might expect by now, obeys the scope, nesting, and inheritance rules:

There *is* only One Mind. (Text, p. 50)

Christ ... abides within the Mind that is His Source [i.e. God]. (W-pII.6)

the Christ Mind is yours. (Text, p. 108)

we are of one Mind, and that Mind is ours. (Text, p. 169)

[God's] Mind created all that is, ... (W-263.1)

...I was created in [God's] Mind... (W-326)

I am ... in the Mind of God. (W-119.3)

you are ... in the Mind of God... (Text, p. 272)

you dwell in the Mind of God ... (Text, p. 224)

you cannot be anywhere *except* in the Mind of God. (Text, p. 213)

your mind is part of God's. (W-36.1)

My mind is part of God's. (W-35)

life is of the mind and in the Mind. (Text, p. 152)

you are a mind, in Mind and purely mind... (W-158.1)

So, we (the many souls) are minds within Christ, who is a mind within God, who is also a mind (further instances of the *nesting* rule). Or, alternatively: We, the many souls, inherited our minds from Christ, who inherited his mind from God (further instances of the *inheritance* rule); and so we inherited the mind of God. Thus:

You think with the Mind of God. (W-45.2)

it is [God's] Mind with which you think. (W-92.3)

God is the Mind with which I think. (W-59.5)

What do minds do? They create ideas and thoughts:

Ideas are of the mind. (Text, p. 490)

A thought is in the mind. (W-167.3)

And:

Every mind *must* project, because that is how it lives... (Text, p. 174)

projection is a law of mind. (Text, p. 252)

So that, since

Projection is a fundamental law ... by which you ... were created. (Text, p. 174),

then it follows that:

God created His Sons by [projecting] His Thought... (Text, p. 146)

The Thought of God created you [via projection]. (W-165.2)

Creation is the sum of all God's [projected] Thoughts... (W-pII.11.1)

creation ... [is a projected] Idea of God... (Text, p. 376)

Thus, God created world C and its entities (including our selves/souls) by projecting ideas/thoughts from (actually, *within*) his mind; which suggests that *mind is the basic agent of creation*. Indeed:

only mind can create at all... (Text, p. 597)

mind creates all things that are, ... (W-167.6)

5.2 Our inherited ability to create

The following passages reveal that we (the many souls, i.e. our minds) inherited the ability to create from God:

Everything [God] created is given *all* His power because it is part of Him and shares His Being *with* Him. (Text, p. 176)

The soul, because of its own likeness to its Creator, is creative. No child of God is capable of losing this ability, because it is inherent in what he *is*. (Text, p. 601)

You were created through [God's] laws ... and the manner of your creation [by which you inherited the likeness of God] established you as creators. (Text, p. 219)

...I am an Effect of God, and so I have the power to create like [God]. (W-326)

the Sons of God...were created as creators. (Text, p. 145)

...God Himself created you *as* a creator. (Text, p. 155)

God created you to create. (Text, p. 146)

your function...is creation... (Text, p. 251)

God gave you the function to create in eternity. (Text, p. 204)

How do we create?:

Projection...is a fundamental attribute of God, which he also gave to his Son. In the creation, God projected his creative ability out of Himself toward the souls which He created, and also imbued them with the same [ability] to create... (Text, p. 601)

Projection is a fundamental law ... which *always* operates. It is the law by which you create and were created. (Text, p. 174)

...I am an Effect of God, and so I have the power to create like [God]. (W-326)

you *can* create as [God] did, ... (Text, p. 209)

In other words, we create via the *same* method that God used to create us (and world C in general), i.e. *by projecting ideas and thoughts* — which makes sense, since we inherited our ability to create *from* God.

Now the question is, *what* (for example) do we create?:

Your mind is capable of creating worlds... (Text, p. 222)

You, too, have a Kingdom which your Soul has created. (Text, p. 108)

And:

The world ...was...projected *from* your mind... (Text, p. 245)

The world ... [is] nothing but your own projection... (Text, p. 274)

the world *is* one of [projected] ideas... (Text, p. 124)

There is no world apart from your ideas ... you maintain the world within your mind in thought. (W-132.10)

you *made* the world you see... (Text, p. 413)

The world you see ... is of your own making... (W-14.1)

[Your] ... mind ... *made* this world... (Text, p. 341)

I have invented the world I see. (W-32)

So, in general, each of our souls/minds is “capable of creating worlds” (note the *plurality* of “worlds”). And, in particular, the “world” in the last eight passages refers to the world of our *current* experience, which includes the physical universe. So *we* made the physical universe, world P, by projecting it from our minds.

Of course, much resistance can be expected, at least initially, to the notion that we (i.e. our minds) are capable of having anything to do with the creation of a world such as the physical universe. A first step in getting past this resistance is to disequate our minds with our *brains*, and to disequate our selves with the physical bodies that we are currently associated with. For sure, brains and bodies *are* very limited in their abilities, and certainly not capable of creating the physical universe (indeed, they are products *of* the physical universe). Our *minds*, on the other hand, were inherited from the mind of God, and so (within their nested scopes) have the same creative power as God:

The mind is a very powerful creator, ... (Text, p. 59)

The creative power of both God *and* His Creations is limitless, but it is *not* in reciprocal relationship. ...in Creation you are *not* in a reciprocal relation *to* God, because He created *you*, but you did *not* create Him. We have already stated that only in this respect your creative power differs from His. Even in this world there is a parallel. Parents give birth to children, but children do *not* give birth to parents. They *do*, however, give birth to their children, and thus give birth *as* their parents do. (Text, pp. 158-59)

The part of the last passage that says “in Creation you are *not* in a reciprocal relation *to* God, because He created *you*, but you did *not* create Him” has to do with the ontological *priority*, and thus *scope*, of God’s creation in relation to the scopes of our own creations. That is, our creations are ontologically *subsequent*, and thus their scopes are nested/confined/encapsulated

within the scope of God’s creation (world C). It follows that the scopes of worlds that we, the many souls, have a hand in creating (such as world P, the physical universe) are logically nested *within* the scope of world C — and so such nested worlds may be called *bubble* worlds. It also follows that, given the logical nesting of our creations, it is *outside* the scope of our creative abilities to *change* anything that God created, including our own souls (more about that in section 9).

Now consider the following passage:

The Kingdom is the result of premises, as much as this world is. (Text, p. 177)

In this passage, “The Kingdom” refers to the first-created world, i.e. the world created by the original projections from God, which in terms of the present model is the world generated by system C, or world C; and “this world” refers to the world of our current experience, which includes the physical universe, i.e. the world generated by system P, or world P.

In light of the above results, the passage tells us that ideas/thoughts which are held by the creator of a world become *premises* (and/or, if you will, configuration *parameters*) which shape the nature of that world, and that this was indeed the case for the construction of worlds C and P. Among the most fundamental of these premises would be the *four postulates* for constructing any (generic) world (section 4.2) — which, due to their overarching scope, could only have come from the mind of God. So, when we henceforth speak of “God’s premises”, we include among them the four postulates, as well as other ideas/thoughts that are deemed to have their source in the mind of God.

In system C, therefore, the initial projection, \mathbf{d}_{0c} , is a one-dimensional vector which *carries* ideas/thoughts from its source — God — into the created Kingdom, or world C. Due to the scope rule pertaining to \mathbf{d}_{0c} , these ideas are in effect/operant at level 1 and above in world C, and thus act — in a Platonic way — as ubiquitous premises/parameters within the ordinary space of that world. Likewise, for system P, the initial displacement, \mathbf{d}_{0p} ⁹, carries ideas/thoughts that are in the mind of its creator-soul into the construction of the physical world, which, due to the scope rule, act as premises and parameters that are in effect — also in a Platonic way — *everywhere* within the ordinary space of that world. Such ideas/premises/parameters thus provide a mechanism for the “fine tuning” of worlds. And, it may be noted, the use of the word “premises” in this passage, as well as the nature of their *scopes* just given, together with the datum that *mind is the agent of creation*, support the notion (stated in [2]) that *the process for constructing a world follows the form of a logical derivation* (more about that in section 7).

An example of one of God’s premises — besides the four postulates — follows next.

5.3 The axiom of equality

Just as all electrons in the physical universe (world P) are considered to be identical, so also it might be expected that their counterparts in world C, our souls, are all identical — i.e.

⁹In the system-P paper we denoted the fundamental displacements as \mathbf{d}_0 , \mathbf{d}_1 , \mathbf{d}_2 , etc; but in the present paper we are adding a ‘p’ in the subscripts to clearly indicate that they are displacements/projections for system P.

that they (or *we*, the many Sons/souls) all have exactly the same inherent nature, attributes, properties, and abilities. This is affirmed by ACIM in the following passages:

They [the many Sons] are all the same ...and equal... (Text, p. 273)

all of God's Sons are of equal value, and their equality is their Oneness. (Text, p. 235)

There is no difference among the Sons of God. (Text, p. 492)

God is *not* partial. ...all of his gifts are given freely to everyone alike. (Text, p. 37)

My [Jesus'] will cannot *overcome* yours, because *yours is as powerful as mine*. If it were not so, the Sons of God would be unequal.¹⁰ (Text, p. 186)

The mind that was in me [Jesus] is in you, for God creates with perfect fairness. (Text, p. 136)

My [Jesus'] mind will always be like yours, because we were created as equals. (Text, p. 127)

awe is not appropriate in connection with me [Jesus], *because* of our inherent equality. (Text, p. 69)

Thus, God's founding premises constructed a world ("the Kingdom", to use ACIM's term; world C, to use our term) in which his many Sons (the souls) were created "with perfect fairness", and therefore are all equal, the same, identical. We will refer to this as God's *axiom of equality*, and may consider it to also be one of God's founding premises.^{11,12}

¹⁰Note that, according to ACIM, Jesus is our *peer*. That is, like us, he is a soul, or one of the many "Sons" (who, at one time, was also associated with a human body here on earth). Thus, in terms of the present model, Jesus (or, rather, his *soul*) is an entity/being at level 2 of system C. And so it follows that Jesus is *not* the single entity at level 1 of system C, i.e. the one Son, or Christ (although, like us, Jesus *did* inherit the complete nature of Christ).

¹¹Note that the "axiom" of equality can possibly be *derived* from an argument similar to the one we used (in [1] and [2]) to derive, e.g., the uniformity (isotropy and homogeneity) of the ordinary 3-dimensional space of a world. That is, differences among the souls would have to be conferred directly by God; but, since God is independent of the souls, then he must manifest and operate *uniformly* to all of them, and so the attributes that they inherit from God must be distributed uniformly to each of them. In other words, the equality of souls is a *symmetry* property that, like possibly every fundamental symmetry, is rooted in an underlying *independence relation*, which is itself rooted in a relation of ontological priority.

¹²The notion of soul equality can be unwelcome to egos — since, as elaborated later, egos are all about *specialness*. A computer analogy, however, can help alleviate some unnecessary anxiety: The computers that people have on their desktops (or in their hands) these days are all basically identical in their capabilities and functionalities. Nevertheless, there is an infinite number of things that people can do with these machines; and, in general, everyone *is* doing (or creating) something different with *their* machine, according to their own wills and desires. Thus, even though our souls and minds are created identical, by changing the *state* of our minds each of us is capable of doing and creating an infinite number of different things with them:

Creation is ... in number infinite, and everywhere without all limit. (W-pII.11.1)

And, according to some of the ACIM passages quoted above, such creation *is* our function.

5.4 Ideas/thoughts obey the nesting rule

Since ideas/thoughts are *constructed* by a mind-source, then that source is *prior* to those ideas/thoughts; and, conversely, the constructed ideas/thoughts are *subsequent*. Thus, by the nesting rule (or, if you will, the nesting *law*), we expect ideas/thoughts (or any *grouping* of them, comprising a *thought system*) to be nested, embedded, encapsulated, or contained within their mind-source. Indeed:

ideas leave not their source. Such is creation’s law... (Text, p. 491)

ideas leave not their source... (W-132.10)

ideas leave not their source. (W-156.1)

thoughts do not leave their source. (W-45.2)

No thought...can leave the thinker’s mind... (Text, p. 424)

no thought system transcends its source. (Text, p. 233)

Ideas do not *leave* the mind which thought them in order to have separate being. (Text, p. 132)

Of course, this raises the following question: If ideas/thoughts never leave their mind-source, then how do minds *communicate* with each other? The answer to this question will be developed in (a future) section 11, where we will discuss communication in general.

6 The physical universe (world P) is a branch *off of* the projection sequence for world C

Where is world P located in relation to world C? Since C is prior, and P is subsequent, then it follows from the nesting rule that (the scope of) world P is contained *within* (the scope of) world C. Thus, as already determined above, world P (the physical universe) is a kind of *bubble* world/universe that is logically nested *within* world C. We may therefore think of world P as *branching off of* the sequence for world C.

Where along the sequence for world C does this branching take place? Since *we* “made” the physical world, and we are the souls (beings at level 2), then it is appropriate to locate the branching point at *level 2* of world C, as illustrated in Fig. 4. This suggests that level 0 of system P (i.e. “losp”) is the same as, or coincides with, level 2 of system C (“lusc”); that is, $losp = lusc$. Which raises the next question: With respect to *ourselves*, the souls, *where* is the physical universe located?

In general, the relation between a creator and its creations is that the former is *prior*, and the latter are *subsequent*. Thus, by the nesting rule, a creation must be embedded, contained, or nested *within* its creator. Indeed, we found that *God’s* creations — world C and its entities, spaces, etc. — *are* wholly nested within God, as supported by the passage:

Fig. 4: System/world P (the physical universe) is shown here as a *branch off of* level 2 of system C, which is justified by the finding that *we* (the souls) are beings at level 2 of system C, and the ACIM statement that *we* “made” the physical world.

God...encompasses *all* Being... (Text, p. 120)

This applies likewise to our *own* creations:

Your creations ... [are] in you, as you ... [are] in God. (Text, p. 159)

Thus, if *we* made the physical world (as previously-quoted ACIM passages claim), then we are *prior* to that world, and it is *subsequent*; so, by the nesting rule, the physical world should be wholly contained *within* us. However, our present *experience* appears to contradict this: we, the souls (or at least the seven billion of us here on earth), *seem to be nested within the physical universe* (not the other way around) — and thus the physical world seems to be mostly *outside* of us (not wholly *inside* us). In other words: If we made the physical world, then how did we get *inside* of it?; or, conversely, how did the universe get *outside* of us?

This problem regarding our place with respect to the physical universe — i.e., whether *it is within us*, or *we are within it*, or somehow both — will be resolved in the next section.

7 Our place with respect to the physical universe (and other bubble worlds): Scope/nesting inversion

Repeating the problem noted above: The creation of world C *obeys* the nesting rule (i.e. the first-created world is wholly contained within its creator, God), whereas *our* creation of world P seems to *violate* the nesting rule (i.e. the physical universe appears *not* to be wholly contained within *us*; rather, we seem to be contained within *it*). The following passages give clues to resolving this seeming inconsistency:

the truth is very simple; *all power is of God*. (Text, p. 230)

the power to create is of God. (Text, p. 133)

of yourselves you can do nothing. (Text, p. 192)

you [the many souls/Sons] are co-creators with [God]... (Text. p. 159)

you are co-creator with God... (Text, p. 210)

...[God] has made you co-creator of the universe along with Him. (Text, p. 544)

Thus, whereas God can create *by himself*, we cannot create anything *by ourselves*; rather, we *co-create with* God. And so we co-created world P with God. Which raises the question: What is *our* role in such co-creation, and what is *God's* role?

From the passages

Projection is a fundamental law of the mind, and therefore one which *always* operates. It is the law by which you create... Every mind *must* project... (Text, p. 174)

The mind is a very powerful creator, and it never loses its creative force. It never sleeps. Every instant it is creating, and *always* as you will. (Text, p. 59)

what you project is up to you, but it is *not* up to you *whether* to project, for projection is a law of mind. (Text, p. 252)

we conclude:

- *We*, the many souls, choose/select/determine the ideas/thoughts that are held in our minds; that is, we choose the *ideational content* (or *state*) of our minds, which corresponds to what we desire (i.e. “*always* as you will”). Our choice of ideational content may be referred to as the *ideation action*.
- The (ideational) content of our minds is *always*, automatically, being projected. The projection of our mental content may be referred to as the *projection action*.
- That the projection action is *automatic*, and therefore beyond our control, suggests that its cause/source is independent of, and thus prior to, our minds. That the projection action is “fundamental” implies that its source must be God at level 0.

Thus, *our* role in co-creation is to develop/choose the *content* and desired output (i.e. *what* is to be projected), and *God's* role is to perform the actual projections. In this sense, God, or God's mind, acts as a kind of projection *engine* or *function*, if you will, which is always operating — always projecting the ideational content of our minds, and thereby always producing the output that we want (again, “*always* as you will”). It follows (by analogy with mathematics and computer programming) that the ideas/content that a soul-mind

provides to the co-creation process may be thought of as *arguments* to God's projection function. A different choice of ideas/arguments constitutes a different *invocation* of God's projection function, which produces a different output. As such, the soul who supplies the content/arguments that spawn, e.g., a new bubble world may be called the *invoker* of that world.

In the creation of world C, therefore, God performed *both* the ideation and projection actions himself. In the creation of bubble worlds (such as world P, the physical universe), however, *we* perform the ideation action, and God performs the projection action. In other words, whereas God is the *sole* creator of world C (which includes the creation of our souls), we are *co-creators* (with God) of bubble worlds *within* world C.

Indeed, it can be argued that this division of labor, so to speak, between God and the souls, in creating bubble worlds, is *necessary*. That is, due to God's overarching scope, any world that he creates directly must encompass *all* of creation; which likely means that God by himself can create only *one* world — what we call world C. So, to create worlds that are nested *within* world C (i.e. bubble worlds) *requires* the existence and participation of *subsequent* entities/minds that are also within world C; i.e., the dependence of bubble worlds on our existence and participation makes them *subsequent to* — and thus nested *within* — world C. It follows that God *depends on* us, the souls — acting as his proxies, if you will — to *extend* creation within world C:

You who belong in God have the ... function of extending His [creation]... (Text, p. 184)

God and the Souls He created *are* symbiotically related. They are *completely* dependent on each other. The creation of the Soul itself [by God] has already been perfectly accomplished, but the creation *by* Souls has not. God created Souls so He could depend on them [to extend creation within world C]... (Text, p. 48)

God is as dependent on you as you are on Him, because *his* autonomy *encompasses* yours, and is therefore incomplete *without* it. (Text, p. 232)

In other words, God and the many souls he created are completely dependent on each other, but in different ways, as follows: (a) We, the souls, are *existentially* dependent on God, but God is not existentially dependent on us (i.e., God created us; we did not create him). (b) To *extend* creation *within* world C, our existence and participation (e.g. our choice/input of ideational content) are absolutely necessary; so God completely depends on us in those regards.

In creating a bubble world, therefore, we (the souls) provide the content of our minds as input (the ideation action), and God performs the actual projection (the projection action). The content that we provide, in the form of ideas/arguments, determines the premises/parameters (fine-tuning or otherwise) for the newly-generated world, which in turn determine the properties of that world, i.e. the specific output. Thus, differences between bubble worlds are solely attributable to differences in the ideational content or arguments that *we*, the souls, supply to the process. It is in this sense that some of the ACIM passages

above — e.g. “you *made* the world you see”, “The world you see...is of your own making”, “I have invented the world I see” — have their meaning.

With the above results in mind, we can now address the main issue of this section: How did we get *inside* of a bubble world that we “made”, when the scope/nesting rules seem to imply that such a world should be nested/contained within *us*? The short answer is that we made only the *ideational content*, not the projections themselves; i.e., the *content* that we made is indeed contained within our minds (“ideas leave not their source”), but the projection sequence itself is not, as we now elaborate.

Since God and (arguably) his projection action are *prior to* the invoker-soul, then the projection/displacement sequence that generates a bubble world is *also* prior to the invoker; i.e., the invoker is *subsequent* to that sequence. By the nesting rule, therefore, the invoking soul will be embedded/nested *within* the bubble world that is so generated. Thus, e.g., for the case of world P, upon completion of the projection action (by God) — which generates the sequence ($\mathbf{d}_{0p}, \mathbf{d}_{1p}, \mathbf{d}_{2p}, \mathbf{d}_{3p}$) — the invoking soul will find itself *within* world P.

However, because a soul controls the content of its own mind, then it is free to change/edit that content at will. So, if a soul chooses to edit from its mind the content that was needed to invoke a given bubble world, thereby replacing it with a different content, then the *new* ideational content will be projected, with the result that that soul will no longer be within that world. Thus, the invoker of a bubble world (e.g. the physical world, world P) is *not* stuck in that world, but is able to *exit* it, as affirmed by the following passages:

You are [not bound] to the world you made. (Text, p. 430)

the world you made ... has [no] power to [contain] its maker. (Text, p. 430)

In this sense, the invoker of a bubble world is just a *subscriber* to that world, and is free to *unsubscribe* at will.

As we have described, the invoker of a bubble world first develops and chooses a set of ideas/thoughts (constituting a thought system), which is then carried along with the projection sequence into the newly generated world, thereby acting as premises for, and otherwise “fine tuning”, that world. Consequently, upon execution of the projection action (by God), the invoking soul will find itself nested *within* the very bubble world that it invoked and fine tuned. Thus, even though the fine-tuning ideas/thoughts/premises of the bubble world are *within* the mind of its invoker, that invoker will see those thoughts manifesting *outside* of itself (as seemingly global premises):

you see only ... [your] thoughts projected outward. (W-8.1)

Your picture of the world can only mirror what is within. (W-73.5)

Ideas leave not their source, and their effects but *seem* to be apart from them. Ideas are of the mind. What is projected *out*, and seems to be *external* to the mind, is *not* outside at all, but an effect of what is in, and has *not* left its source. (Text, p. 489; underline mine)

In other words, this effect seems to *invert* the scopes of the thinker and his own ideas/thoughts; that is, the ideas are *actually* nested within the *thinker's* mind or scope — but after the projection action, the thinker seems to be nested within (or subsumed under) *their* scope. We may therefore refer to this effect as a **scope inversion** — or, alternatively, a **nesting inversion**. A scope/nesting inversion thus *elevates* ideas/thoughts *within* the thinker's mind to the status of premises, or even axioms, which the thinker can then *seem* to be subject to, even dependent on. (Indeed, the thinker/subscriber's *experience* in a generated bubble world *is* dependent on these ideas/premises.) As indicated above, such scope/nesting inversion is due to the *projection action* being performed by *God*, which makes that action *prior* to the soul and its particular set of ideas/thoughts.

The axiom of equality implies that anything created with the mind of God must be *equally shared* among *all* of the souls; for, to be otherwise would render souls unequal, thereby contradicting that axiom. So, since everything we (the many souls) create is actually *co-created* with God, then:

The creations of every Son of God are yours, because every creation belongs to everyone, being created for the Sonship as a whole. (Text, p. 177)

Consequently, once a bubble world has been invoked and produced (using God's projection action), the invoking soul itself has no special status, relation, or privilege with respect to that world; and so it follows that a bubble world is *equally* accessible (by subscription) to *all* of the souls. In other words, any soul can enter/join any bubble world simply by *subscribing* to (at least some of) its projected premises (thereby yielding a scope inversion, by which the soul finds itself inside that world); and, conversely, a soul can *exit* a bubble world by *unsubscribing* from those premises. In this way, individual souls can enter and exit bubble worlds at will. The *invoker* of a bubble world is thus merely the *first subscriber* to that world, and it is not really important who that invoker is; indeed, he may choose to exit that world, while others remain subscribed to it. Of course, all of this applies to the bubble world of our current, common, experience — the physical universe, or world P: its invoker became the first subscriber; then other souls (e.g. yours and mine) entered/joined this world by later subscription, and may choose to exit it by unsubscribing.

The *plurality* in the passage “Your mind is capable of creating worlds” indicates that souls can invoke any number of bubble worlds within world C, with each generally having *different* ideational content, and thus different premises/parameters/properties. It follows that the physical universe of our current experience may be just one of many such possible bubble worlds, with spaces generated by relations between the displacements/projections of its sequence (as described in detail in [2]), and with a particular set of ideas/premises to fine tune it according to the will/purpose of its invoker. From all indications, it seems that one of the invoker's main purposes for making this physical universe was to produce a world that could support the formation of *biological life*, as we know it.

At the invocation of a bubble world, and with the advent of the *second* displacement in the sequence, *time* comes into being and the clock of that world starts ticking from $t = 0$ seconds (as described in [2] for world P). Joining/entering souls, we may suppose, then

subscribe to that clock at its *present* value, as seen from within that world. Consequently, a soul entering the physical universe today would be subscribing to its *current* clock value of around $t = 13.8$ billion years — thus making subscription to a bubble world analogous to a *magazine* subscription, for which the issues that you receive *begin* with the *current* one.

In summary, the construction of a bubble world is a collaborative co-creation between a soul and God. The soul’s contribution to the process is to develop and choose the ideas that will invoke and fine tune the world with premises/parameters (and thus properties) according to its purpose; God’s contribution is to actually generate the projection sequence. *Both* contributions (the soul’s and God’s) are *necessary* to create a bubble world; neither by itself is sufficient. Thus, the creation of a bubble world is *dependent* on both God and the invoking soul; conversely, since the soul is not bound to that world, then he is actually *independent* of it. So the only world that a soul is actually “bound” to, or dependent upon, is the first-created world, or world C; i.e. world C is the only world that a soul cannot unsubscribe from.

That a soul can experience the *inside* of a bubble world (whose premises/parameters it is ontologically and existentially independent of) is the result of a scope/nesting inversion, which is an effect caused by the fact that God, who performs the projection action, is *prior* to the invoker/subscriber; and so the nesting rule places the soul *within* the bubble world that it invoked or subscribed to. But, as described above, the soul’s independence from the content of a bubble world means that it can *unsubscribe* from those worlds at will.

Once the invoking soul chooses the ideational content, the *design* of a bubble world is “in the can”, so to speak, and will be projected/executed (by God’s action). The *differences* between bubble worlds are thus down to the different choices of ideas/content that are specified by the invoking soul. Therefore, depending on the ideational content that the invoker provides to the process, bubble worlds can presumably range from simple to complex. The physical universe, having many parameters, would then be an example of a *complex* bubble world.

A *simple* bubble “world”, on the other hand, might consist of just a single idea which, upon projection and scope inversion, becomes elevated to the status of a premise or supposition/hypothesis in the mind of the invoker, under which the invoker’s subsequent thinking is then subsumed. A sequence of such projected ideas would yield a sequence of nested hypotheses or hypotheticals, and thus could form part of a standard logical derivation (e.g., in the system known as Natural Deduction, or ND; see [14], [15], and [16]). Such simple processes might therefore constitute the steps of our ordinary thinking and reasoning. Indeed, given that we (the many souls) are apparently *not* creating new, many-parametered worlds (like the physical universe) every instant, then presumably the mental content that we typically develop is of this simple, or “plain vanilla”, variety. Such projected simple content might yield bubble “worlds” that, in contrast to the physical universe, have space and time dimensions that are patently of mental origin, character, and utility — which may therefore contribute to the ability of our minds to perform spatio-temporal reasoning.

If a soul is subscribed to a complex bubble world, then it may see things/events as happening within the ordinary space of that world (as in the case of our current experience,

in which we see events happening within the physical universe). However, since a soul is free to choose the content of its own mind, then it may choose to *not* be subscribed to *any* complex bubble world, in which case it will likely see things/events as happening within the ordinary space of the first-created world, or world C; and so we might say that such a soul *remains plainly within world C*.

In any case, echoing our results above (and from [2]), the construction of a world — whether world C, or a bubble world (simple or complex) within world C — *is a mental process that follows the form of a logical derivation*. The “mental” part of this statement comes from our earlier finding that all creation is in mind, and of mind. The rest of the statement, in addition to being supported by previous findings, has an *a priori* argument in its favor, as follows.

Suppose we accept the following two propositions:

1. The general process for constructing/deriving worlds must be the **simplest possible** process (we might call this the *maximum parsimony requirement*).
2. The process must be comprehensible.

To be comprehensible, the process must be *logical*. But the simplest-possible logical process for constructing/deriving something would presumably just be a form of logical derivation itself; that is, the process would follow the basic form of a logical derivation. QED.

Recall now that, in creating world C, God performs *both* the ideation and projection actions *by himself*; i.e., he does not depend on a *prior entity* to perform the needed projection action (by definition, *there is no prior entity*). Therefore no scope/nesting inversion takes place, and God *does not* find himself nested/contained within his creation, world C; rather, being subsequent to God, world C is *wholly* encompassed within *him*. This suggests that God himself cannot manifest as a personal or particular entity within world C; rather, he can only manifest universally, ubiquitously, uniformly, and abstractly throughout it:

[God’s communication/interaction with his creation] is perfectly abstract, in that its quality is universal in application, ... (Text, p. 120)

This is of a piece with our earlier result that God cannot create *bubble* worlds by himself, since any world created solely by God must have overarching/universal scope, and thus be equivalent to world C itself. So, the ability to be subsumed under one’s own hypotheticals is something that we, the many souls, *can* do, but God *cannot* do.

Similarly, if a soul could construct a bubble world (such as the physical universe) *by itself* (i.e., performing *both* the ideation and projection actions, with a *prior* entity, God, playing no part), then no scope/nesting inversion would take place, and so that soul could not manifest as a personal/particular entity *within* that bubble world. So the fact that the projection action is actually executed *by the mind of God*, and is thus *prior* to the subscribing

souls, creates a kind of loophole — or *wormhole* even — by which souls can enter into, and participate within, their bubble worlds in a *personal* way (i.e. as personal beings, as we find ourselves to be right now in the physical universe, world P).

In the particular case of world P, the above allusion to a “wormhole” refers to our subscription to at least some of the displacement sequence ($\mathbf{d}_{0p}, \mathbf{d}_{1p}, \mathbf{d}_{2p}, \mathbf{d}_{3p}$) by which we gain access to the spaces of that world — since the *first* displacement in that sequence, \mathbf{d}_{0p} , being *one*-dimensional, would then become a sort of wormhole or *tunnel* through which a soul moves from being plainly within world C, to being within world P, or vice versa. Of course, the passage of a soul through a “tunnel” on moving from/to the physical world is a common feature of near-death and other transcendent experiences.

Since a soul is free to subscribe, or not subscribe, to any bubble world, then we will assume that it is also free to choose *how much* of a bubble world it subscribes to — with the one requirement that, to enter/join a bubble world, one must at least subscribe to the *first* projection in its sequence; which, for world P, is \mathbf{d}_{0p} . But, of course, by only subscribing to \mathbf{d}_{0p} , a soul would then have a “view” of world P from the combined perspectives of level 1 and level 0, from which viewpoints \mathbf{d}_{0p} would be *one*-dimensional. We might then say that such a soul has entered only so far as (or has halted itself within) the “entrance tunnel” to world P. However, if the soul also chooses to subscribe to the projection \mathbf{d}_{1p} , then its view of world P will include the perspective of *level 2*, in which case \mathbf{d}_{0p} will be (from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_{1p}) *three* dimensional (as described in [2]); and so the soul’s view or experience would include the ordinary, three-dimensional space of world P. Furthermore, as we found in [2] for *particles* at level 2 and above (e.g. electrons, protons and neutrons), such a soul would see itself as nested/embedded within that ordinary space (in [2] we called this “the standard perspective”).

Thus, if a soul in world P (the physical universe) wishes to associate with a human body (which is composed of electrons, protons and neutrons), then that soul presumably must subscribe to at least the projections \mathbf{d}_{0p} and \mathbf{d}_{1p} , by which it will see itself as nested within the ordinary space of that world (which comports with our present experience). In this sense, a soul that has chosen to associate with a human body will have a perspective of world P that is *native* to level 2, since that is the first level at which *both* \mathbf{d}_{0p} and \mathbf{d}_{1p} are operant (again, this is called the “standard perspective” for that world).

Given the control that we have over the content of our minds, we will assume that a soul can also *selectively* subscribe to the ideational content or premises of world P (or any bubble world, for that matter). The more of these ideas of world P that one subscribes to, the more fully one experiences that world as designed by its invoking soul. Note, however, that, even though a soul may be *in* world P, and as much as it may subscribe to the premises of that world, a soul is never *of* that world. Souls are *of* world C alone (the world in which they were created by God). Thus, while a soul may be able to *experience* aspects of world P in a personal and sensorial kind of way (depending on how much of that world it has subscribed to), that soul is *never actually subject to* the particular premises or “laws” of world P (e.g. the laws of physics). So, for example, souls that have subscribed to world P are not subject to the *forces* of world P; which implies e.g. that they are unaffected by

gravity and electromagnetism, and can thus travel right through walls or other physical “barriers”, etc. Nonetheless, as alluded to above, the soul’s *experience* of a world *does* depend on the ideas that it has subscribed to; e.g., a soul that has associated with (or, if you will, *subscribed to*) a human body may then see itself as being subject to physical forces (although, in actuality, it is not).

Finally, let us reiterate the main results of this section: The part of the co-creative process that we (the many souls) are responsible for — i.e. the set of ideas/premises that determine the particular parameters/properties of a bubble world — is indeed contained *within* our minds (and leaves not its source). But, upon projection of those ideas by God, the scope-inversion effect then changes our perspective to being *within* the bubble world that we have co-created or subscribed to, whereby the content of our mind seems to be outside of us. We can then choose to unsubscribe from that bubble world by changing/editing the content of our minds.

8 The world of our current experience is a *miscreation*

Our selves in the present world exhibit a multitude of differences and inequalities — in terms of health, wealth, status, power, abilities, talents, intelligence, etc. Such differences, however, clearly contradict God’s axiom of equality, and are therefore absurd and false. But the world’s absurdities and contradictions do not stop there.

In general, this world exhibits a myriad of *opposites*: true/false; positive/negative; action/reaction; for/against; friend/foe; good/evil; innocence/guilt; love/hate; life/death; rich/poor; health/sickness; construction/destruction; creation/annihilation; order/disorder; offense/defense; winners/losers; victory/defeat; peace/war; haves/have-nots; privileged/unprivileged; intelligent/unintelligent; abundance/scarcity; and so on. Indeed, opposites seem to be at the very core of what this world is all about, resulting in many paradoxes and absurdities — such as life depending on death, peace depending on war, etc. Although we may be accustomed to accepting opposites as “normal”, here is what ACIM says about them:

The truth is simple; it is one, *without* an opposite. (Text, p. 484)

Truth cannot have an opposite. (W-152.3)

truth...has no opposite and cannot change. (Text, p. 567)

nothing but the truth exists...because what is not true *cannot* exist... (Text, p. 80)

There is no opposite... There is no contradiction to the truth. (W-138.4)

opposites do not exist. (Text, p. 236)

an opposite to God does not exist. (W-167.1)

What is opposed to God does not exist... (W-137)

God and His Son ... *have* no opposite... (Text, p. 295)

Creation knows no opposite. But here [in the present world] is opposition part of being “real”. (W-138.2)

From these passages we may define God’s *axiom of unity*, as follows:

The truth is *one*, without an opposite; opposites do not exist.

So the world of our present experience, brimming with inequalities and opposites, stands in contradiction to God’s axioms of equality and unity. Or, as ACIM puts it:

[This world is] a battleground, where contradiction reigns and opposites make endless war. (M-27.2)

this world *is* the opposite of Heaven, having been made to *be* its opposite. And *everything* here takes a direction *exactly* opposite to what is true. (Text, p. 332)

earth...is Heaven’s opposite in every way. (W-131.7)

what...must be the truth...clearly contradicts the world. (W-132.7)

Not one thing in this world is true. (W-240)

this strange world you made ... *is false*. (Text, p. 269)

By these passages and the axiom of unity, therefore, the present world (including the physical universe itself) is a *false* world. Moreover, since “creation knows no opposite”, and yet the present world is rife with opposites, then this world cannot be a true creation, and must therefore be a *false* creation, or *miscreation*.

What is the *cause* of this false, miscreated world? To answer this, we first recall that the construction of a world follows the form of a logical derivation (sections 5.2 and 7). Second, we note that, if one’s logic is *valid* (i.e. truth-preserving), then a false conclusion or output implies that one or more of the *premises* is false. Third, we take the following passage from ACIM,

[Your] logic is as impeccable as that of [God]... (Text, p. 133),

to affirm that the *logic* by which we construct worlds *is* indeed valid. We conclude, therefore, that the present world is false because one or more of its founding ideas/thoughts/premises is false. Of course, as described above, *we* are the authors of (or, at least, *subscribers to*) those premises. So, to borrow from Shakespeare, the error is not in our stars, but in our own minds:

all thoughts have power. They will either make a false world or lead me to the real one. ... the world I see arises from my thinking errors ... My thoughts cannot be neither true nor false. They must be one or the other. What I see shows me which they are. (W-54.1. (16))

What I see is the projection of my own errors of thought. (W-51.1)

There is little doubt that the mind can miscreate. (Text, p. 596)

Furthermore, since ideas/thoughts never leave their source, then the false idea(s) that miscreated the present world, with its endless absurdities, must still reside in the minds of its subscribers.

According to ACIM, a single motive lies at the root of all of our false ideas and miscreations: the desire for *specialness*, in relation to other souls. Such *relative* specialness is a condition in which one's self/soul is better than, or superior to, other souls. Because it contradicts God's axiom of equality, however, this kind of specialness is impossible. It can be desired, imagined and pursued, but never realized — and so it may also be called *false* specialness. In the words of ACIM:

specialness...takes many forms, but always clashes with the reality of God's creation...
(Text, p. 449)

what is specialness but an attack upon the Will of God? (Text, p. 451)

what is One can *have* no specialness. (Text, p. 492)

The last passage indicates that “specialness” also contradicts the axiom of unity, as will soon be elaborated.

To be sure, we (the many souls) are all *absolutely* special, in the sense that we are creations of God, and have inherited all of his attributes, including the ability to create worlds. But the key aspect of this type of specialness, which may be referred to as *absolute* or *true* specialness, is that, in accordance with the axiom of equality, none of us is *more* special than anyone else; that is, we *all* inherited exactly the same attributes from God, in exactly equal amounts. So none of us is better than, or less than, anyone else:

[true] specialness does *not* stem from exclusion, but from inclusion. *All* [souls] are [absolutely] special. (Text, p. 26)

Absolute specialness is something we already have, so there is no need to desire, seek or pursue it. Relative specialness, on the other hand, is something we don't have, and so it became an object of desire and pursuit. From now on, the term “specialness” will mean *relative* specialness, unless otherwise noted.

According to ACIM, we (that is, each of us, individually) first tried, and failed, to obtain specialness by seeking special favor from God:

you asked for special favor, and God did not give it. (Text, p. 261)

God gives no special favors... (M-25.2)

God ... *knows* no special love... ...*no-one is special* [in the relative sense]. (Text, p. 312)

That is, given our perfect equality, it is impossible for God to favor or love any one of us more than another; for, to give special favor, God would be contradicting his own axiom of equality. Our failure to obtain specialness directly from God, however, did not deter us from desiring it:

You wanted specialness to be the truth. (Text, p. 460)

So we pursued it by other means — in essence, by simply making it up in our minds:

Forgive [God] the specialness He could not give and yet you made instead. (Text, p. 454)

Our method for mentally fabricating specialness involves comparing ourselves with others and deeming them to be *inferior* in some way — which, of course, makes us *superior*, and thus relatively special. As ACIM puts it:

Specialness *always* makes comparisons. It is *established* by a lack seen in another, and maintained by searching for and keeping clear in sight all lacks it can perceive. This does it seek, and this it looks upon. ... Against the littleness you see in [another] you stand as tall and stately, clean and honest, pure and unsullied by comparison with what you see. (Text, p. 451)

specialness not only sets apart, but serves as grounds from which attack on those who seem “beneath” the special one is “natural” and “just.” (Text, p. 450)

Thus, for a mind to think of its self/soul as special relative to another, it must perceive the other as something *less than* special, thereby spawning oppositions such as “I am superior, the other is inferior”, “I am good, the other is not good”, “I am good, the other is *evil!*”, etc. So the *will to specialness*, in addition to violating the axiom of equality, engenders the idea of, and belief in, *opposites* — and thus also violates the axiom of unity.

The idea of opposites, held in a mind, then becomes a founding premise for any world that is constructed by that mind — entering that world with the first displacement/projection in the sequence (\mathbf{d}_{0p} , in the case of the present physical world) and, by the scope rule, staying in effect for all subsequent projections, thereby operating ubiquitously throughout it as a sort of (negative) Platonic Idea; in other words, the idea of opposites becomes *axiomatic* for that world. Since opposites are operant in the bubble world of our present, common experience (i.e. the physical universe), we conclude that that world is the product of a soul whose mind invoked a displacement/projection sequence while engaged in the will to specialness.

The minds of other souls (after the invoker) then enter this bubble world by subscribing to (at least some of) its projection sequence and premises (including the idea of opposites), and its clock value — and exit it by unsubscribing. This means that, to enter the physical world (and, moreover, to become associated with a physical body), even someone like Jesus (i.e. his *mind*) may have needed to subscribe to its premise of opposites.

According to ACIM, however, Jesus is a

completely True Witness for God. (Text, p. 17),

by which we infer that he did/does not *believe* in any false ideas, such as specialness or opposites. This suggests that *subscription* to a bubble world and its premises may not require *belief* in those premises. So, again, it may be similar to a *magazine* subscription; that is, one may subscribe to a magazine without actually believing any of its content (e.g. an economist who is a staunch free-market capitalist may subscribe to a Marxist magazine for purely instructive/research purposes). In general, then, we suppose that a given subscriber's level of belief in the ideas/premises of a bubble world may be somewhere on a scale between no belief and strong belief.

A larger excerpt than the last one above,

...I [Jesus] am the *only* completely True Witness for God. [italics mine],

implies that, while *Jesus'* belief in the false premises of this world is/was exactly zero, for the other souls currently here on earth the level of belief is *greater than zero*; that is, in entering the physical world, we not only *subscribed* to false premises, but to some extent we *believed* them. And for the *invoker* of a false world, we may suppose that the level of belief in the false premises (and their corresponding world) is rather strong, since:

What you project you believe. This is an immutable law of mind in this world as well as in the Kingdom. (Text, p. 160)

All creation rests on belief... (Text, p. 41)

9 Aspects of creation and miscreation

Just as a false premise constructs a false world, so also true premises construct a *true* world (again, this is due to the logical validity — i.e. truth preservation — of the process). Thus, the fundamental difference between a created (i.e. *truly* created, or *sound*) world and a miscreated (i.e. *falsely* created) world is that *all* of the founding ideas/premises are true in the former, whereas at least one premise is false in the latter.¹³ Therefore, only *one* false idea/thought/premise is needed to initiate a sequence of miscreation:

¹³In logical terms, therefore, a world is true if the *conjunction* of its founding premises is true; and false if that conjunction is false, i.e. if one or more of the premises/conjuncts is false.

the chain of miscreation...can arise out of even the simplest mis-thought. (Text, p. 72)

ACIM generally reserves the words “create” and “creation” for reference to *true* creation only, and uses the words “make” and “making” in reference to *false* creation (miscreation). Thus, world C was *created* by God, and the physical universe (world P) was *made* by us, the souls. In some contexts, however, the words “create” and “creation” are used in a generic sense, and may thus refer to either true creation or false creation (as may also be the case in this paper); an example of this is a passage recently quoted above: “All creation rests on belief...”, which applies to both true creation and miscreation. In addition, to capture the *generic* sense of the terms “create” and “creation”, I often simply use the *neutral* terms “construct” and “construction”.

As already noted above, the plurality of the passage “Your mind is capable of creating worlds” indicates that each of our minds is capable of constructing *many* (probably an unlimited number of) bubble worlds; and we now know that these worlds can be either true or false. The physical universe is just *one* such bubble world (of the false/miscreated variety), invoked by one mind/soul, and subsequently subscribed to by many others.

9.1 Conjoining true and false premises

It follows from above that the ideational *content* of a miscreation may consist of a conjunction of false *and* true ideas/thoughts/premises; and so a miscreation may contain aspects of it that are true, and are therefore creations. For example, in the making of world P, while the idea of opposites is false, the actual projection of it, which is performed by the mind of God, is true.

Miscreation is still a genuine creative act in terms of the underlying *impulse* [i.e. *projection*], but *not* in terms of the *content* of the creation. (Text, p. 62)

And since, e.g., the ordinary three-dimensional space of world P derives from \mathbf{d}_{0p} , \mathbf{d}_{1p} , and the postulates (all of which, by themselves, are arguably true) (sections 4 and 4.2), then we could say that that space is a true aspect of world P. Thus, in this sense, the construction of world P is part creation and part miscreation. However, the *conjunction* of creation and miscreation makes the resulting system as a whole a *miscreation* — just as in logic, where the conjunction of any number of true premises with just one false premise yields a false/inconsistent/miscreated *system*.

9.2 Creation, miscreation, and reality

Consider the following passages:

what *is* real except the Creations of God and those which are created like His? (Text, p. 190)

only what God creates, or what [a mind] creates with the same will, has any real existence. (Text, p. 80)

nothing but the truth exists...because what is not true *cannot* exist... (Text, p. 80)

Anything that God creates is as true as He is. (Text, p. 146)

what is true is everything that God created. (Text, p. 120)

the laws of God ... are true. (Text, p. 165)

God made no contradictions. (W-131.7)

only [what] is true ... is *real*. (Text, p. 155)

Thus, *God creates only truth*, and *only truth is real*. So *reality must be true*, and based on truth *alone*. This implies that God's premises are *all* true; i.e. God *never* indulges in false ideas/thoughts/premises. It follows that God *only* creates, and *never* miscreates.

Likewise, if all of *our* ideas/thoughts/premises are consistent with God's (i.e. if we are of the "same will" as God), then, and only then, do we (truly) *create* — and those creations, too, are *true* and *real* (since then, in accord with the first passage above, our creations "are created like His"):

[God's] ideas alone establish truth. (W-325.2)

Your creations *are* the logical outcome of [God's] premises. *His* thinking has established them *for* you. (Text, p. 177)

The Son's creations *are* like [God's]. ... His union with [the mind of God] is the *source* of his creating. *Apart* from this, he *has* no power to create... (Text, p. 413)

the mind as God created it *is* capable of creating reality. (Text, p. 134)

That is, God's thinking (and projecting) has established his true thoughts as operant and accessible everywhere in world C; and we use those ideas/thoughts as premises to logically derive our own real/true creations. Since,

the sum of all God's Thoughts [is] ... in number infinite, and everywhere without all limit. (W-pII.11.1),

then the range of our own co-creations (with God) is also infinite in number. (See also footnote 12.)

Given that *reality is based on truth alone*, and that miscreation stems from the holding (and projecting) of one or more *false* ideas, then it follows that:

miscreation is *not* real... (Text, p. 63)

the miscreations of the mind do not really exist. (Text, p. 597)

miscreation ... does not exist at all at the level of true Creation. (Text, p. 42)

no miscreation exists. (Text, p. 85)

Thus, for example, world P, the physical universe, is *not* real, since it is based on at least one premise — e.g., the idea of opposites — that is false:

a world in opposition to God's Will ... cannot have reality, because it never was created. (W-200.7)

[You made] a world of total unreality ... in which *everything* is backward and upside down... (Text, p. 356)

this world is not real... (W-53.2)

this world is a hallucination ... you made it up... (Text, p. 408)

the world you see has nothing to do with reality. It is of your own making, and it does not exist. (W-14)

the world does not exist. (W-132.8)

This world is but [a] dream... (Text, p. 526)

Nevertheless, we *believe* that our miscreations are real and true:

miscreation ... is always invested with reality. (Text, p. 64)

miscreation is *necessarily* believed in by its own creator... (Text, p. 42)

All beliefs are real to the believer. (Text, p. 96)

when you *believe* something you *have* made it true *for you*. (Text, p. 170)

All things I think I see reflect ideas. ... What I see reflects a process in my mind, which starts with my idea of what I want. From there, the mind makes up an image of the thing the mind desires, judges valuable, and therefore seeks to find. These images are then projected outward, looked upon, esteemed as real and guarded as one's own. From insane wishes comes an insane world. From judgment comes a world condemned. (W-325)

Such misbelief is likely assisted by the fact that, because the process is *valid* (i.e. truth-preserving), then belief in a premise entails belief in its consequents. Due to their lack of reality, however, and as indicated by the above passages, miscreations of our minds (such as world P, the physical universe) are mere fantasies, illusions, dreams — made by us in order to fulfill our desire for specialness. Furthermore, the “dream” reference in one of the passages above implies that, when involved in false ideation, with consequent miscreation (and scope inversion), the condition of our minds is likened to a state of *sleep*:

[God's] ideas reflect the truth, and mine apart from [God's] but make up dreams. (W-325.2)

The special ones are all asleep...lost in dreams of specialness. (Text, p. 455)

you have put yourself to sleep, and dreamed a dream... (Text, p. 518)

you dream a dream...[whose] content is not true. (Text, p. 518)

In ACIM, (true) creation is sometimes referred to as “extension”, since it *extends* the truth and reality of God and his co-creators:

Creation is the means for God's extension. (Text, p. 447)

...God has created by extension. (Text, p. 223)

God created His Sons by extending His Thought and retaining the extensions of His Thought in His Mind. (Text, p. 146)

...God's creative Thought proceeds *from Him to you* ... [and] so must *your* creative thought proceed *from you to your* creations. In this way only can *all* creative power *extend outward*. God's accomplishments are *not* yours. But yours are *like* His. ... You *have* the power to *add* to the Kingdom... (Text, p. 159)

...God created you by extending *himself as you*, [and] you can only extend *yourself* as He did. ... God extends...beyond limits,...and you, who are co-creators with Him, extend His Kingdom forever and beyond limit. (Text, p. 159)

[True] Projection...is the law of extension. (Text, p. 174)

Given that (true) creation (now also called extension) requires exclusively true ideas/premises, then it follows that extension requires *knowledge* of truth:

The *extension* of truth, which *is* the Law of the Kingdom, rests ... on the knowledge of *what truth is*. (Text, p. 161)

And the following passages indicate that the way to possess such knowledge of true premises, and thereby avoid the pitfalls of miscreation, is to involve the mind of God not only at the projection stage of the co-creation process, but also at the (earlier) stages when we are developing/selecting the ideas/premises:

My real [/true] thoughts are the thoughts I think with God. (W-51.4. (4))

God Himself has established what you can project with perfect safety. (Text, p. 156)

Your [true] creations *are* the logical outcome of His premises. *His* thinking has established them *for* you. (Text, p. 177)

it is the *agreement* of their Thought that makes the Son a co-creator with the Mind Whose Thought created him. (Text, p. 473)

That is, true co-creation is not a *pure* division of labor in which we arbitrarily develop the content by ourselves and God merely performs the projection action; rather, it also requires that we *co-create the content with God*. Such due diligence on our part ensures that all of the content that we input to the creation process is true, which ensures that the output is true and real.

Now consider these passages:

what God creates is eternal. (Text, p. 130)

God created *only* the eternal... (Text, p. 235)

...God created *only* the changeless. (Text, p. 151)

[God's] Creations are changeless. (Text, p. 160)

what God has Created...is perfect...[and cannot] be rendered imperfect... (Text, p. 601)

Reality is changeless. (Text, p. 553)

Whatever is true & real is eternal, & *cannot* change or be changed. (Text, p. 28)

Thus, not only are God's creations true and real, but they are also *perfect, eternal* and *changeless*, and can never be rendered otherwise. Likewise, our *own* (true) creations — being that they are like God's creations, and thus part of reality — are also perfect, eternal and changeless. Given our earlier result that only what God creates, and what we create like him, is real, then it follows that *reality is perfect and eternal*; and so, as a corollary, whatever is imperfect or perishable *is not real* — i.e. it is an *illusion*. We therefore conclude again that the physical world — where everything is perishable — is not real. Furthermore:

The [physical] world ... cannot have been created by [God]... God created *only* the eternal, and everything [in this world] is perishable. (Text, p. 235)

[this] world could not have been created by [God's] Mind... (Text, p. 467)

Since our *souls* were created by God (as part of world C), then they too are real, perfect, eternal, and changeless — and cannot be rendered otherwise:

God created Souls...perfectly. (Text, p. 48)

[the Soul] has...been created perfect. (Text, p. 601)

every Son of God ... is perfect... (Text, p. 250)

I am as God created me. (Text, p. 571)

As [God] created me I have remained. (W-326.1)

as you were created ... [so] *you are*. (Text, p. 318)

As God created you, you must remain unchangeable... (W-152.5)

You are and will forever be exactly as you were created. (W-93.7)

Whatever is true & real is eternal, & *cannot* change or be changed. The Soul is therefore unalterable... (Text, p. 28)

The Soul always remains changeless... (Text, p. 29)

So, whatever false ideas/thoughts/premises we might hold in our minds, and despite their absurd consequents (such as the making of the present false world in which, due to the scope-inversion effect, a myriad of personal afflictions seem to be possible and real), our souls remain eternally perfect, untouched by falsity and illusion:

What God creates is safe from *all* corruption, unchanged and perfect in eternity. (Text, p. 466)

[God] keeps what *He* created safe. *You* cannot touch it with the false ideas you made, *because* it was created not by you. (Text, p. 461)

your own perfect immunity...cannot be assailed. (Text, p. 142)

The term “salvation” does *not* apply to the Soul, which is not in danger and does not need to be salvaged. (Text, p. 107)

the Soul is already perfect, and therefore does not require correction [from error; i.e. “salvation”]. (Text, p. 597)

Thus, while the *experiences* of our minds *do* vary, depending on the premises that we have subscribed to and believe in, our souls themselves do not change at all, and so need no saving.

The second ACIM passage above indicates that the immunity of our souls from the false ideas/constructions/actions of our minds follows directly from the scope rule: God’s creation of souls is *prior* to our minds’ own actions (which are thus *subsequent*); so, by the scope rule, the soul itself is *outside the scope* of our actions, and therefore cannot be changed by them:

Everything is limited in some way by the manner of its creation. [Your] Creator...set the limits on [your] ability to miscreate... (Text, p. 55)

reality [has not] been taken from its throne by your mistakes. (M-18.3)

So the scope rule (which stems from postulate 4, and thus from God’s premises) is, among other things, a kind of beneficial limitation — or *safety feature*, if you will — which prevents us from harming God’s creation in general (including our own souls, and other souls). Likewise, our *own* (true) creations — having been co-created with God, using only true ideas — are also perfect and eternal, and thus outside the scope of our minds to change; and so we cannot even harm *them* with our miscreations:

Everything that was created is ... *perfectly* safe, because the laws of God protect it...
(Text, p. 214)

God has kept [your own real/true creations] very safe in *His* knowing while your attention has wandered. (Text, p. 118)

9.3 Dichotomies: Useful and unuseful

From our conclusion that opposites do not exist (the axiom of unity), together with the passage

evil...does not exist. (Text, p. 75),

it follows that “good and evil” is *not* a correct/true/real dichotomy of existence. Furthermore, this dichotomy has no positive, instructive value, since its use (I would argue) typically includes the meaning: “*I* am good — *others* are evil”. That is, while ostensibly violating only the axiom of unity, its main purpose is to violate/deny the axiom of *equality*, and thus to *establish* specialness.

Likewise, “truth and falsity”, “creation and miscreation”, “reality and illusion”, are also not correct/true/real dichotomies of existence, because (a) they constitute opposites, which do not exist, and (b) falsity, miscreation, and illusion *themselves* do not exist (the latter *by definition*). However, as their use necessarily violates *only* the axiom of unity (not the axiom of equality), these three dichotomies can serve a positive, useful, instructive, and thus meaningful purpose — i.e., as a step in the right direction — by helping to *disestablish* specialness:

only two categories are meaningful... And of these two, but one is real. ... The one answer to all illusions is truth. (M-8.6)

That is, the two meaningful (i.e. positive, useful, and instructive) categories of existence are (1) truth, reality, creation; and (2) falsity, illusion, miscreation. But only the first of these categories is actually real.

Finally, consider the passage:

There *is* no hell. Hell is only what [your false beliefs have] made *of the present*. (Text, p. 304)

Thus, hell does not actually exist; and any hells that *seem* to exist are caused by the false ideas within our minds, which, via projection and scope inversion, produce false bubble worlds that we find ourselves nested within (but can exit whenever we choose). Consequently, like the others discussed above, “heaven and hell” is not a real dichotomy of existence. It may be a useful dichotomy, however, provided we remember that all of the hells that we experience are of our *own* making.

9.4 Parts of our minds

Since the content of our minds is always being projected, then a sequence of ideas/thoughts in our minds yields a sequence of *projected* ideas/thoughts, which may also be called a *thread*. Such a thread constitutes a *part* of the mind that spawned it. Segments or sub-parts of a given thread are related by ontological priority and subsequence; thus the scope, nesting, and inheritance rules apply. For example, an idea that is operant at one point in a thread *stays* operant at all subsequent points; i.e., those subsequent points or levels in the thread are nested within the scope of the prior idea, and thereby *inherit* it.

Prior to our belief in false ideas (e.g. specialness and opposites), our minds produced only true thoughts, which were projected, yielding a sequence/thread of true creations. Let us refer to this true sequence as “thread T”. (The thread T’s in each of our minds may be considered as extensions of *God’s* thread T, by which he created system/world C, including our souls and minds, as illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2.)

Our subsequent belief in false ideas, however, then initiated a sequence of false creations (miscreations) which may be called “thread F” (this happened in each of our individual minds; so we each have our *own* thread F). At some point along one mind’s thread F, the premises/parameters for system/world P were invoked and projected, yielding the physical universe as a part of the invoker’s thread F. Other souls/minds (e.g., yours and mine) then subscribed to system P, thereby making the physical universe part of *their* thread F’s (if any; i.e., perhaps the minds of some souls, such as Jesus, had no thread F?). Thus, a more detailed Fig. 4 might have shown system P branching from a thread F at some point; that thread F branching from a thread T; and that thread T branching from level 2 of system C.

Our threads T and F may therefore be considered as the two major parts or divisions of our minds:

there are only two parts of your mind. One is ... made up of illusions. The other is ... where truth abides. (W-66.7)

As already alluded to, the world that we are currently experiencing (which includes world P, the physical universe) is a part of the thread F (if any) in our minds. If we exit world P, but continue to hold false ideas in our minds, then we *remain* within thread F. Thus, exiting the physical world (e.g. when our bodies die) does *not* bring automatic salvation from (our fabricated hells of) falsity and illusion:

Many think that [salvation] is accomplished through death, but *nothing* is accomplished through death... *Everything* is accomplished through life, and life is of the mind and in the Mind. (Text, p. 152)

The world [of falsity and illusion] is not left by death but by truth... (Text, p. 97)

correction belongs at the thought level, ... [since] the Soul is already perfect, and therefore does not require correction. (Text, p. 597)

Salvation is nothing more than “right-mindedness”... (Text, p. 107)

That is, the full return to truth and reality (i.e., “salvation” from falsity and illusion) is accomplished not by the death of our bodies (nor Jesus’ body, for that matter); rather, it is accomplished by (the *mental* action of) unsubscribing from the thread-F part of our minds. Such unsubscription may be achieved simply by the *denial* of specialness, which has the effect of reinstating in our minds (and *projecting*) God’s axiom of equality — which is exactly what the Golden Rule is all about:

Denial should be directed only to error [e.g. specialness], and projection should be limited to truth [e.g. equality of souls]. ... The Golden Rule...work[s] effectively...on this basis. (Text, p. 50)

10 The creation and miscreation of meaning

We construct the *meaning* of a string of words (e.g. an English sentence) by (a) applying our learning, beliefs, and experience (including experience with the words and their different arrangements); and (b) applying context. Such learning, beliefs, experience, and context are necessarily *prior* to the meaning that is constructed from them — that is, they constitute *premises* that are available and operant in our minds to *subsequently* construct meanings for words and strings of words.

Similarly, in the present model, the construction of meaning seems to follow the same basic paradigm. In [2], for example, \mathbf{d}_{1p} constructs the meaning “ \mathbf{d}_{0p} is a three-dimensional space” by invoking/applying postulate 4, which (being one of God’s premises) is *prior* to both \mathbf{d}_{0p} and \mathbf{d}_{1p} . This suggests the following **semantic principle**:

The meaning of a (created) thing is constructed by referencing, or invoking/applying, things that are *prior*.

Due to the scope rule, the *prior* things (which are referenced/invoked/applied) are operant/available/accessible to play their role in generating the meaning of the subsequent thing.¹⁴

¹⁴The semantic principle is, it seems, another corollary of postulate 4; i.e., the meaning of a (created) thing is *dependent* on something that is *prior* to that thing.

In general, then, the meaning of one thing depends on something prior, whose own meaning in turn depends on something *more* prior, and so on. So, ultimately, *all* meaning depends on the *most* prior thing; that is, all meaning is constructed by reference to God, or by invocation/application of his premises/axioms:

there *is* only one meaning. This Meaning comes from God and *is* God. (Text, p. 162)

meaning itself is of God. (Text, p. 198)

[God is] the Source of meaning. (W-rV.in.12)

In other words, God and his premises are the *ultimate arbiters* of all meaning. Indeed, to expand on the example above, postulate 4 of system P is inherited from (and thus depends on) postulate 4 of system C, which itself comes from God's premises/axioms, whose source is of course God himself at level 0 of system C. So, it would be correct to say that the meaning " \mathbf{d}_{0p} is a three-dimensional space (with respect to \mathbf{d}_{1p})" is constructed by applying God's premises, and thus that this meaning comes from God himself.

Since the construction of meaning requires an unbroken chain of reference going back to God or his premises, it follows that if/when this chain is broken it is not possible to know the (real/true) meaning of anything:

to be without [God] *is* to be without meaning. (Text, p. 324)

You cannot see alone. ...*nothing* you see means *anything* alone. Seeing *with* [God] will *show* you ... all meaning... (Text, p. 295)

Indeed, the holding of a *false* idea/premise (e.g. the premise of opposites) in our minds, with its consequent illusions, requires that we *do* break the **semantic chain**; for, if the chain were not broken, then the contradiction of our false premise against God's true premises would be obvious, and the falsity could not be maintained:

illusions ... will *not* stand before [the truth]. (Text, p. 455)

To understand *how* the semantic chain is broken, recall that *every* idea/thought in the mind of a soul is *projected*, and is thereby (via scope inversion) elevated to the status of a *premise* which the soul finds its state of mind to be subsumed under (i.e., nested within the scope of). Such premises then become what may be called *local arbiters* of meaning; that is, the mind will apply these *local premises* to determine the meanings of things (by, e.g., using the premises to logically derive conclusions, and thus interpretations, of/about those things). If the local premises are consistent with God's premises, and are therefore *true*, then they are the same as, equivalent to, or an extension of, God's (global) premises, and so the semantic chain goes all the way back to God, and thus is *not* broken. The result of this *unbroken* semantic chain is *true meaning*, and so the mind's true ideas/thoughts/premises produce an *extension* of truth and reality.

If, on the other hand, a local premise is *inconsistent* with God's premises, i.e. it is *false*, then belief in it constitutes a *denial* of truth and reality,¹⁵ with effects as follows:

All vision starts *with the perceiver*, who judges what is true and what is false. And what he judges false [i.e. what he *denies*], *he does not see*. (Text, p. 269)

never underestimate the power of denial ... [for] *you* can give it the power of *your* mind, whose power is without limit of *any* kind. If you use it to deny reality, reality is gone *for you*. ...denying any part of [reality] means you have lost awareness of *all* of it. (Text, p. 172).

That is, belief in *any* false idea/premise banishes truth/reality from our vision and awareness, thereby breaking the semantic chain:

When you made what is *not* true visible, what is true became *invisible*. (Text, p. 254)

With the semantic chain broken, the false local premises (forming a false *local context*) assume the mantle of "ultimate" arbiters of meaning in our minds, and are then used to derive *false* interpretations/meanings for *everything*, with the result that:

you do not know *what anything* [truly] *means*. (Text, p. 311).

And, as a corollary, because false meaning is the same as *no meaning* (since nothing false actually exists), then a consequence of believing in, and thus interpreting with, any false idea/premise is that everything constructed in that context is *meaningless*. For instance, in constructing or subscribing to world P (the physical universe), we typically believe (to one degree or another) in its false founding premises (the ideas of specialness and opposites), which we then use to interpret (i.e. derive the meaning of) that world and everything in it. So it follows that:

This world is meaningless... (Text, p. 473)

The world you made is ... without [true] meaning of *any* kind. (Text, p. 245)

how questionable are [the world's] premises, how doubtful its results... Learning that stops with what the world would teach stops short of meaning. (W-184.7)

In general, then, due to the process of projection and scope inversion, the ideas that we hold within our minds are elevated to the status of premises/arbiters by which we interpret/construct the meaning of whatever world we are in. As ACIM puts it:

The world can give you *only* what you gave it, for being nothing but your own projection, it *has* no meaning apart from what you found in it, and placed your faith in. (Text, p. 274)

¹⁵For example, belief in specialness is a *denial* of God's axiom of equality, and belief in opposites is a *denial* of God's axiom of unity.

Projection makes perception; the world you see is what you *gave* it, nothing more than that. ... It is the witness to your state of mind, the *outside* picture of an *inward* condition. As [you] thinketh, so [do you] perceive. (Text, p. 409)

perception *is* a wish fulfilled. (Text, p. 489).

Thus, if we hold *only* true ideas/premises in our minds, then we see a world of (true) meaning. On the other hand, if we hold false ideas/premises, then that world has the false “meaning” that we gave it and had faith in (i.e., that we wished for, and believed in).

The moral of this story is that our thoughts are not to be taken lightly; for they *always* produce large-scale effects — either extending truth and reality, or yielding (in the perception of the thinker) whole worlds of falsity and illusion:

There is no more self-contradictory concept than that of “idle thoughts.” What gives rise to the perception of a whole world can hardly be called idle. Every thought you have contributes to truth or to illusion; *either* it extends the truth or it multiplies illusions. (W-16.2)

The truth is that there *are* no “idle thoughts”. *All* thinking produces form at some level. (Text, p. 60).

Fortunately, the previously-quoted passage,

reality [has not] been taken from its throne by your mistakes. (M-18.3),

and the scope rule itself, tell us that our false thinking does not, and cannot, dethrone God’s premises or reality in general: they are still operant throughout all of creation, and it is beyond our scope to affect them in any real way. That is, as indicated above, when we engage in false thinking by holding false ideas in our minds, we merely lose *awareness* of truth and reality, and (due to scope inversion) become immersed in illusion; but reality itself is unchanged.

One might think, however, that the ubiquity and sheer power of God and his *real* and *true* premises would simply *crush* our opposite, false premises, and thereby *force* them out of our minds — thus making it *impossible* to break the semantic chain. But the following passages give some clues as to why this is not so:

God’s Will does not oppose. It merely is. (W-166.10)

Reality opposes nothing. (Text, p. 434)

...God Himself would not go against [your will] ... [and] Nothing God created can oppose your will, as nothing God created can [in reality] oppose His. (Text, p. 187)

In other words, since falsities are not real, then nothing can really oppose God/truth; and, conversely, there *is* nothing for God *to* oppose. Thus, God/reality/truth do not oppose or attack anything. So it follows that false ideas will remain in our minds — breaking the semantic chain, and producing false interpretations/meanings for everything — until *we* ourselves choose to stop believing them.

10.1 False premises generate a false self identity — the ego

We have determined that the false ideas of specialness and opposites, when held in our minds, are (upon projection and scope inversion) promoted to the rank of local premises or axioms under which we are subsumed. These premises are then used to derive other (false) ideas, beliefs, interpretations, conclusions, or meanings for and about *everything* — including our own selves/souls, other souls, and God. False ideas/beliefs about one’s own self constitute a *false self identity*, which ACIM calls the *ego*:

The ego *is* ... a confusion in identification... (Text, p. 175)

The ego is ... a *part* of your belief about yourselves. (Text, p. 117)

the ego is an idea... (Text, p. 103)

[The ego’s] existence *is* dependent on your mind, because it is a *belief*. (Text, p. 175)

the mind ... made the ego... (Text, p. 104)

the ego is part of your mind... (Text, p. 246)

The ego *is* the part of the mind which believes in division. (Text, p. 133)

That is, the ego is the part/thread of our minds that believes in, and (due to scope inversion) is subsumed under, the ideas of specialness and opposites, and thus believes in dividing everything and everyone into categories of opposites (such as special/unspecial, good/bad, good/evil, etc). Since the ideas of specialness and opposites are only operant in our minds under thread F, then the ego is the part of our minds that corresponds to thread F and its branches (which includes the physical universe).

Given its basis in false ideas, however, it follows that:

The ego *is* a contradiction. (Text, p. 99)

the ego is ... an illusion... (Text, p. 333)

The ego ... is nothing more than a delusional system... (Text, p. 223)

the ego is not you. (W-25.2)

the ego is *not* the [real] self. (Text, p. 105)

the ego is nothing... (Text, p. 227)

Because the falsities in our minds are contained under thread F, then we can say that the ego is a creature of that thread and its branches, or that that part of our minds is the *realm* of the ego. Consequently, upon unsubscribing from thread F (and thus unsubscribing from the ideas of specialness and opposites), we rejoin the part of our minds (thread T; section 9.4) where *only* truth is operant, and where the ego does not “exist”:

there are only two parts of your mind. One is ruled by the ego, and is made up of illusions. The other is ... where truth abides. (W-66.7)

While our minds are *subscribed* to the realm of the ego (thread F), however, we will (as concluded above) harbor false ideas/beliefs about our selves. For example, recall that our *true* function is to extend creation (by co-creating ideas, thoughts, meaning, worlds, etc., with God). Under the influence of the ego, however, our true function is dropped from awareness, and the ego's drive for specialness becomes our new "function".

A lot more could be said about the ego's abnormal psychology; but, for our limited (metaphysical) purposes here, an important point is that *no two egos can ever agree on the meaning of anything*:

conflicted minds *cannot* be faithful to one meaning... (Text, p. 161)

beliefs of the ego *cannot* be shared... (Text, p. 207)

That is, each ego is founded on the premise of its *own* specialness, which is necessarily at the expense of *others'* specialness; and so, e.g., every ego has a different idea of who the special one is (itself), and who the unspecial ones are (everyone else). With the ego's own specialness established as the basic axiom of its thought system, every subsequent idea, thought, premise that the ego constructs will follow *from* that axiom and be consistent with it (and be in the service of sustaining it). It is thus impossible for two egos to hold the *same* set of premises from which they could arrive at the *same* beliefs, interpretations, or meanings for and about things.

For minds to agree on, or *share*, meaning, and thereby avoid this semantic problem, they must agree on a *common* set of premises from which common/shared meaning can be derived. But the only premises that fit this description are ones that are consistent with *God's* premises — e.g. the axioms of equality and unity. For instance, the use of God's premises to interpret "specialness" will yield the *absolute* sense of that term (as defined in section 8), which is a meaning that all of us *can* share. On the other hand, the use of our *own* (i.e. the *ego's*) premises to interpret "specialness" yields the *relative* sense of that term, which is a meaning that we *cannot* share (since each ego sees *itself* as the special one, and others as unspecial). Which brings us full circle: To arrive at true, consistent, common, shared beliefs and meaning, minds must refer questions of meaning back to God and his premises, and thus *not* break the semantic chain. Obviously, an *ego* will never do this; for then it would be exposed for what it is — an illusion. The path back to true meaning therefore involves *denying* the ego — i.e., "throwing our ego under the bus", if only for an instant.

11 Communication

...Still to come...

12 The separation — and return

...Still to come...

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References

- [1] White, P.B.: New fundamental principles for physics (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6029908>
- [2] White, P.B.: A fundamental model for constructing the physical universe (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5937913>
- [3] Van Cleve, J.: Dependence. In: Audi, R. (ed.) *The Cambridge Dictionary of Philosophy*, pp. 191–193. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK (1995)
- [4] Wapnick, K.: *Absence from Felicity: The Story of Helen Schucman and Her Scribing of A Course in Miracles*, 2nd edn. Foundation for A Course in Miracles, Temecula, CA (1991)
- [5] Sweet, R.W.: FACIM/FIP v. Endeavor, 96 Civ. 4126 (RWS), Opinion. United States District Court, Southern District Of New York (2003). https://web.archive.org/web/20031204161206/http://www.jcim.net:80/Copyright/Endeavor_trial_transcripts/03-08697.pdf
- [6] Howe, C.M.: *Never Forget To Laugh: Personal Recollections of Bill Thetford, Co-Scribe of A Course In Miracles*. Self published (2009).
- [7] Jesseph, J.R.: William Newton Thetford Professional Vita. <https://web.archive.org/web/20190726191944/www.miraclestudies.net/BillVita.html>
- [8] Wapnick, K.: The History of the Manuscripts of *A Course in Miracles* (2007). <https://acim.org/archives/editing-history/>
- [9] Perry, R.: The Earlier Versions and the Editing of *A Course in Miracles* (2004). <https://circleofa.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/BetterWay47.pdf>

- [10] *A Course In Miracles*, 3rd edn. Foundation for Inner Peace, Mill Valley, CA (2007)
- [11] *Text* volume of the Urtext of *A Course in Miracles* (UPE-Ready edition). Urtext for Planet Earth (UPE) (2003). <https://web.archive.org/web/20051107145754/http://acim.miraclevision.com:80/urtext/acim-urtext-2003-upe-ready-edition.pdf>
- [12] *A Course in Miracles: The Text, Workbook for Students, and Manual for Teachers*. The Little Garden (2008). The *Workbook for Students* begins on page 428 of the pdf, and the *Manual for Teachers* begins on page 706. <https://web.archive.org/web/20151110053310/http://www.thelittlegarden.org/acim.pdf>
- [13] American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language, 5th edn. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt Publishing Company (2011)
- [14] Pelletier, F.J.: A brief history of natural deduction. *History and Philosophy of Logic* **20** (1999)
- [15] Indrzejczak, A.: Natural deduction. In: Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy. <http://www.iep.utm.edu/nat-ded/>
- [16] Nolt, J., Rohatyn, D.: *Schaum's Outline of Theory and Problems of Logic*. McGraw-Hill, New York (1988)